

GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards

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Present Status and Progress

This report summarizes the present status and progress of the GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards (BPS), including the following GGOS components associated to the BPS:

- Committee “Contributions to Earth System Modeling” (Chair: Maik Thomas)
- Committee “Definition of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs)” (Chair: Richard Gross)
- Working Group “Towards a consistent set of parameters for the definition of a new GRS” (Chair: Urs Marti)

The BPS is chaired by DGFI-TUM and operated jointly with TUM’s Chair of Astronomical and Physical Geodesy. Further involved partners are GFZ (German Research Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam) and DLR (German Aerospace Centre, Oberpfaffenhofen). The Bureau comprises the staff members, the chairs of the associated GGOS components, as well as representatives of the IAG Services and other entities involved in standards and conventions.

The major activities and progress of the BPS are summarized below:

- A key objective of the BPS is to keep track and to foster homogenization of adopted geodetic standards and conventions across all components of the IAG as a fundamental basis for the generation of consistent geometric and gravimetric products. Towards reaching these goals, the BPS has compiled an inventory of standards and conventions used for the generation of IAG products. This inventory presents the current status, identifies gaps and provides recommendations regarding standards and conventions used for the generation of IAG products.
- In the framework of the renewing of the GGOS website, the BPS closely interacts with the GGOS Coordinating Office regarding the representation of geodetic products. In cooperation with the IAG Services, other data providers and the GGOS Science Panel members, user-friendly product descriptions have been generated and implemented at the GGOS website (see Angermann et al. 2022). Two classifications for the geodetic products have been implemented at the GGOS website:

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- ✓ **Geodetic themes:** Reference frames, geometry, Earth orientation, gravity field, positioning and applications.
- ✓ **Earth system components and space:** Outer and near space, atmosphere, hydrosphere, oceans, cryosphere, solid Earth.
- Concerning the updating of the IERS Conventions, the BPS organized together with the director of the IERS Conventions Center (Nick Stamatakos, USNO) a dedicated session on Standards, Conventions, and Formats in the framework of the Unified Analysis Workshop (Thessaloniki, Greece, October 21-23, 2022, see <https://ggos.org/event/unified-analysis-workshop-uaw-2022/>). The focus of the BPS is on the updating of Chapter 1 “General definitions and numerical standards”. Two recommendations have been provided:
 - ✓ **REC-1:** The BPS recommends that the used numerical standards including time and tide systems must be clearly and consistently documented for all geodetic products (*IAG/GGOS*)
 - ✓ **REC-2:** The BPS recommends that the necessity of a new Geodetic Reference System (GRS) should be further clarified (*WG: Urs Marti*)
- Furthermore, the director of the BPS serves as IAG representative to ISO/TC 211 and UN GGIM “GGRF” Subcommittee on Geodesy (SCoG), mainly to the Working Group “Data sharing and development of geodetic standards”. Updates on standards have been provided as input to the Twelfth UN-GGIM Session (August 3-5, 2022 in New York). The BPS also contributes to the activities of the Committee on Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs) and to the two Working Groups on “DOIs for geodetic data” and “Towards a consistent set of parameters for the definition of a new GRS”.

Ongoing activities and planned actions

According to the BPS Implementation Plan, the activities of the Bureau are divided into three main categories: Coordination activities, specific tasks of the BPS, and outreach activities.

- **Coordination activities:** This category comprises GGOS Consortium meetings (annually), GGOS Coordinating Board meetings (twice per year) and monthly telecons of the GGOS Executive Committee to ensure a regular exchange of information among the GGOS components and to manage the strategic planning and day-to-day activities. Furthermore, external and internal BPS meetings are regularly scheduled to coordinate and perform the operational Bureau work.
- **Specific tasks of the BPS:** A key activity of the BPS is to keep track of the adopted geodetic standards and conventions across all GGOS components as a fundamental basis for the generation of consistent geometric and gravimetric products. This task requires a regular updating of the BPS inventory of standards and conventions used for the generation of IAG products to incorporate the latest developments in these fields. The BPS activities also comprise the interaction with IAG and other entities in the field of standards and conventions, such as the IAG Services, the IERS Conventions Center, the Commission A3 “Fundamental Standards” of the International Astronomical Union (IAU), ISO/TC 211 and the Working Group “Data Sharing and Development of Geodetic Standards” of the UN-GGIM Subcommittee on Geodesy (SCoG). Furthermore, the interaction of the BPS with the Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence (GGCE) is an important issue.
- **Outreach activities:** The BPS supports the GGOS Coordinating Office concerning the updating of the GGOS website, in particular regarding the description and representation of geodetic products. The Bureau also contributes to the generation of GGOS films dedicated to specific

geodetic products (e.g., terrestrial reference frames) to make other disciplines and society aware of geodesy and its beneficial products. In this context, the BPS also supports the Committee on Essential Geodetic Variables towards the definition of such EGVs. Moreover, this category includes the presentation of BPS activities and results at workshops, conferences, and to publish them in scientific journals as well as the contribution to other GGOS outreach activities such as publications, popular articles, brochures, etc.

Reference:

Angermann D., Gruber T., Gerstl M., Heinkelmann R., Hugentobler U., Sánchez L., Steigenberger P., Gross R., Heki K., Marti U., Schuh H., Sehnal M., Thomas M.: GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards: Description and Promotion of Geodetic Products. In: (Eds. Jeffrey T. Freymueller and Laura Sánchez), IAG Symposia, 10.1007/1345_2022_144, 2022.

STATUS REPORT 01-11-2022

GGOS Committee on Earth System Modeling

Maik Thomas
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Present Status and Progress

The committee's activities focusing on further developments of data assimilation and AI algorithms, three-dimensional approaches to consider effects due to surface mass loading, as well as on model error estimates have been pursued. In particular, the following progress could be achieved:

- Evaluation of the potential of neural networks for the improvement of numerical stand-alone and coupled system models;
- Adaptation of global surface mass loading models for the consideration of three-dimensional structures of the Earth's crust and mantle as well as of anelastic effects; evaluation of the sensitivity of the tidal and non-tidal loading response to underdetermined model parameters;
- Qualitative evaluation of existing empirical and numerical global ocean tide models and comprehensive discussion of opportunities and next steps for their improvement; quantitative estimates of third-degree ocean tides and their relevance in background models.

Moreover, a discussion on opportunities for the combination of numerical model components with newly developed algorithms based on artificial intelligence is ongoing. Due to its complexity as well as strategic relevance this will be an important topic also in the following years.

Planned Actions and Milestones

Planned activities in the next year will mainly focus on:

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- Consideration of three-dimensional structures of the Earth's crust and mantle as well as of anelastic effects in surface mass loading models;
- Continuation of investigations of opportunities to constrain dynamically coupled model systems by geodetic observations;
- Feasibility studies regarding the coupling of neural networks with traditional data assimilation techniques and application of the combined approach in stand-alone models.

STATUS REPORT 02-11-2022

GGOS Committee on Essential Geodetic Variables

Richard Gross (NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory)

Present Status and Progress

The GGOS BPS Committee on Essential Geodetic Variables was established in 2018 in order to define a list of Essential Geodetic Variables and to assign requirements to them. Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs) are observed variables that are crucial (essential) to characterizing the geodetic properties of the Earth and that are key to sustainable geodetic observations. Examples of EGVs might be the positions of reference objects (ground stations, radio sources), Earth orientation parameters, ground- and space-based gravity measurements, etc. Once a list of EGVs has been determined, requirements can be assigned to them. Examples of requirements might be accuracy, spatial and temporal resolution, latency, etc. These requirements on the EGVs can then be used to assign requirements to EGV-dependent products like the terrestrial and celestial reference frames. The EGV requirements can also be used to derive requirements on the observing systems that are used to observe the EGVs. And the list of EGVs can serve as the basis for a gap analysis to identify observations needed to fully characterize the geodetic properties of the Earth. During GGOS Days 2017 it was agreed that a Committee within the GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards should be established in order to define the list of Essential Geodetic Variables and to assign requirements to them. This Committee was subsequently established in 2018 and consists of representatives of the IAG Services, Commissions, Inter-Commission Committees, and GGOS Focus Areas.

Planned Actions and Milestones

The planned tasks of the Committee on Essential Geodetic Variables are to:

- Develop criteria for choosing from the set of all geodetic variables those that are considered essential;
- Develop a scheme for classifying EGVs;
- Within each class, define a list of EGVs;
- Assign requirements to each EGV;
- Document each EGV including its requirements, techniques by which it is observed, and point-of-contact for further information about the EGV;

- Perform a gap analysis to identify potential new EGVs;
- Define a list of geodetic products that depend on each EGV;
- Assign requirements to the EGV-dependent products;
- Hold workshops to engage the geodetic community in the process of defining EGVs, determining their dependent products, and assigning requirements to them.

STATUS REPORT 3-11-2022

GGOS WG “Towards a consistent set of parameters for the definition of a new GRS”

Urs Marti

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Present Status and Progress

The main task of this WG is to define a consistent set of parameters and formulas for the definition of a new conventional Global Reference System (GRS). This includes the geometry (size and shape of a reference ellipsoid), the gravity field (normal gravity field of this ellipsoid), physical heights, terrestrial time and Earth rotation.

This new definition becomes necessary because since the introduction of GRS80 (Moritz, 1980) the knowledge in Geodesy has improved a lot (e.g. GNSS, gravity space missions) and the use of the parameters became inaccurate and inconsistent over time. The problem of the permanent Earth Tide was not yet a topic at the epoch of the definition of GRS80. A new set of parameters was published by Groten in 2004 but was not widely introduced in Geodesy. Another source of parameters are the IERS conventions, which do not strictly apply GRS80. The acceptance of the IAG Resolution No. 1 in 2015 which defines the potential at Sea Level (W_0) even increases the inconsistency in the geodetic parameters of the conventional GRS (in GRS80, W_0 is a derived quantity).

The new set of parameters is based on the four fundamental parameters: W_0 (Potential at Reference Level), J_2 (dynamic form factor, “flattening”), GM (geocentric gravitational constant) and ω (angular velocity of the Earth). All these quantities are well observed and monitored by various geodetic space techniques. (This implies, that the semi major axis of the ellipsoid will be a derived parameter).

Most of the defining parameters change with time. This includes seasonal variations and long-term trends. These changes are important and must be considered for the consistency with the ITRF (e.g. ellipsoidal heights). Nevertheless, in order to keep things simple for the user, this time variability will not be treated in the published definition of a new GRS. All quantities will be fixed to the epoch 2010.0. This is the epoch at which the W_0 of the IAG resolution No. 1 is defined.

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All calculations will be done in the zero tide system. Only at the very end, conversion formulas to mean tide and tide-free will be given for all quantities. In order to keep things simple, some very minor terms in this conversion will be neglected.

Planned Actions and Milestones

A draft version of a paper with the calculation of the parameters is available. It has to be finished and discussed in the WG. It follows more or less the structure of the papers by Moritz (1980) and Groten (2004). The progress of the work has been shortly presented in October 2022 at the Unified Analysis Workshop (UAW) of the IERS and GGOS in Thessaloniki by D. Angermann. A point of discussion is still the necessity of a new Geodetic Reference System and thus this needs to be further clarified (see REC-2 in the BPS report).

The calculation of a new set of parameters is one thing. The main problem will be to convince the users to adopt such a system as a new global reference. Many users don't see the necessity to replace GRS80, as they just see it as a conventional model for the conversion of geocentric coordinates or for the calculation of gravity anomalies. Main concerns are the danger of confusion and the necessity to update many software packages. This discussion has still to be lead.

Another question to be answered is the necessity to define a conventional global gravity field model. For many applications (e.g. global height system, reference for local geoid determination), the assignment of such a standard model would have some advantages. For different application we would need a low-resolution satellite-only model and a high-resolution combined model.